

T-Neutrosophic Cubic Set on BF-Algebra

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Abstract: In this paper, the concept of t-neutrosophic cubic set is introduced and investigated the t-neutrosophic cubic set through subalgebra, ideal and closed ideal of BF-algebra. Homomorphic properties of t-neutrosophic cubic subalgebra and ideal are also investigated with some related properties.

Keywords: BF-algebra, t-neutrosophic cubic set, t-neutrosophic cubic subalgebra, t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal.

1 Introduction

Zadeh [33, 34] introduced the concept of fuzzy set. Jun et al. [7] defined interval-valued fuzzy set and discussed its properties. Jun et al. [8] presented the notion of cubic subgroups. Senapati et al. [26] generalized the idea of cubic set to subalgebras, ideals and closed ideals of B -algebra. Imai and Iseki [5, 6] introduced the two classes of algebra which were BCK algebra and BCI-algebra. Huang [4] investigated the BCI-algebra. Jun et al. [10, 11] applied the idea of cubic set to subalgebras, ideals and q -ideals in BCK/BCI-algebra. Neggers et al. [13] defined and studied the B -algebra. Cho et al. [3] studied the relations of B -algebra with different topics. Park et al. [15] studied quadratic B -algebra on field X with a BCI-algebra. Saeid [16] was given the idea of interval valued fuzzy subalgebra in B -algebra. Walendziak [32] proved the conditions of B -algebra. Senapati et al. [21, 22, 23, 24, 31] was introduced the fuzzy dot subalgebra of BG-algebra, fuzzy dot subalgebra, fuzzy dot ideals, interval-valued fuzzy closed ideals and fuzzy subalgebra with respect to t -norm in B -algebra. Senapati et. al. [17, 25] was introduced L -fuzzy G -subalgebra of G -algebra and bipolar fuzzy set which was related to B -algebra. Khalid et. al. [20] studied the intuitionistic fuzzy translation. Many researchers [12, 27, 28, 29, 30] have done a lot of work on BG-algebra which was a generalization of B -algebra. Smarandache [18, 19] introduced the concept of neutrosophic set. Jun et al. [9] introduced neutrosophic cubic set. Barbhuiya [2] studied the t -intuitionistic fuzzy BG-subalgebra. Takallo et al. [37] introduced the MBJ-neutrosophic set, BMBJ-neutrosophic subalgebra, BMBJ-neutrosophic ideal and BMBJ-neutrosophic \circ -subalgebra. G. Muhiuddin et al. [38] studied the neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-number, neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-algebra, neutrosophic quadruple subalgebra

and (positive implicative) neutrosophic quadruple ideal. Park [39] introduced the notion of neutrosophic ideal in subtraction algebra and discussed conditions for a neutrosophic set to be a neutrosophic ideal. Borzooei et al. [40] introduced the concept of MBJ-neutrosophic set, BMBJ-neutrosophic ideal and positive implicative BMBJ-neutrosophic ideal. Jun et al. [41] studied the commutative falling neutrosophic ideals in BCK-algebra. Song et al. [42] investigated the interval neutrosophic set and applied to ideals in BCK/BCI-algebra. Khalid et al. [43] interestingly investigated the neutrosophic soft cubic subalgebra through significant results. Muhiuddin et al. [44] was studied neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-number, neutrosophic quadruple BCK/BCI-algebra, (regular) neutrosophic quadruple ideal and neutrosophic quadruple q-ideal. Muhiuddin et al. [45] investigated the (ϵ, ϵ) -neutrosophic subalgebra, (ϵ, ϵ) -neutrosophic ideal. Akinleye et al. [46] defined the neutrosophic quadruple algebraic structures, also studied neutrosophic quadruple rings and presented their elementary properties. Basset et al. [47] studied integrated neutrosophic ANP and VIKOR method for achieving sustainable supplier selection. Basset et al. [48] studied the type 2 neutrosophic number, score and accuracy function, multi attribute decision making TOPSIS and T2NN-TOPSIS.

The purpose of this paper is to introduce the idea of t-neutrosophic cubic set [t-NCS] and to investigate this set through the concepts of subalgebra, ideal and closed ideal of BF-algebra. Homomorphic image and inverse homomorphic image of t-neutrosophic cubic subalgebra [t-NCSU] and t-neutrosophic cubic ideal [t-NCID] are also studied.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, basic definitions are cited that are necessary for this paper.

Definition 2.1 [32] A nonempty set X with a constant 0 and a binary operation $*$ is called BF-algebra when it fulfills these axioms.

1. $t_1 * t_1 = 0$
2. $t_1 * 0 = 0$
3. $0 * (t_1 * t_2) = t_2 * t_1$ for all $t_1, t_2 \in X$.

A BF-algebra is denoted by $(X, *, 0)$.

Definition 2.2 [1] A nonempty subset S of G-algebra X is called a subalgebra of X if $t_1 * t_2 \in S \forall t_1, t_2 \in S$.

Definition 2.3 [14] Mapping $f: X \rightarrow Y$ of B-algebra is called homomorphism if $f(t_1 * t_2) = f(t_1) * f(t_2) \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$.

Definition 2.4 [23] A nonempty subset I of B-algebra X is called an ideal if for any $t_1, t_2 \in X$, (i) $0 \in I$, (ii) $t_1 * t_2 \in I$ and $t_2 \in I \Rightarrow t_1 \in I$.

An ideal I of B-algebra X is called closed if $0 * t_2 \in I, \forall t_2 \in I$.

Definition 2.5 [33] Let X be the set of elements which are denoted generally by t_1 . Then a fuzzy set C in X is defined as $C = \{ \langle t_1, \mu_C(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$, where $\mu_C(t_1)$ is called the existenceship value of t_1 in C and $\mu_C(t_1) \in [0,1]$.

For a family $C_i = \{ \langle t_1, \mu_{C_i}(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$ of fuzzy sets in X , where $i \in k$ and k is index set, we define the join (\vee) meet (\wedge) operations as follows:

$$\bigvee_{i \in k} C_i = (\bigvee_{i \in k} \mu_{C_i})(t_1) = \sup\{\mu_{C_i} \mid i \in k\}$$

and

$$\bigwedge_{i \in k} C_i = (\bigwedge_{i \in k} \mu_{C_i})(t_1) = \inf\{\mu_{C_i} \mid i \in k\}$$

respectively, $\forall t_1 \in X$.

Definition 2.6 [2] Let two elements $D_1, D_2 \in D[0,1]$. If $D_1 = [(t_1)_1^-, (t_1)_1^+]$ and $D_2 = [(t_1)_2^-, (t_1)_2^+]$, then $\text{rmax}(D_1, D_2) = [\max((t_1)_1^-, (t_1)_2^-), \max((t_1)_1^+, (t_1)_2^+)]$ which is denoted by $D_1 \vee^r D_2$ and $\text{rmin}(D_1, D_2) = [\min((t_1)_1^-, (t_1)_2^-), \min((t_1)_1^+, (t_1)_2^+)]$ which is denoted by $D_1 \wedge^r D_2$. Thus, if $D_i = [((t_1)_i)_i^-, ((t_1)_i)_i^+] \in D[0,1]$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, then we define $\text{rsup}_i(D_i) = [\sup_i(((t_1)_i)_i^-), \sup_i(((t_1)_i)_i^+)]$, i. e., $\vee_i^r D_i = [\vee_i ((t_1)_i)_i^-, \vee_i ((t_1)_i)_i^+]$. In the same way we define $\text{rinfi}(D_i) = [\inf_i(((t_1)_i)_i^-), \inf_i(((t_1)_i)_i^+)]$, i. e., $\wedge_i^r D_i = [\wedge_i ((t_1)_i)_i^-, \wedge_i ((t_1)_i)_i^+]$. Now we call $D_1 \geq D_2 \Leftrightarrow (t_1)_1^- \geq (t_1)_2^-$ and $(t_1)_1^+ \geq (t_1)_2^+$. Similarly the relations $D_1 \leq D_2$ and $D_1 = D_2$ are defined.

Definition 2.7 [1,22] A fuzzy set $C = \{ \langle t_1, \mu_C(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$ is called a fuzzy subalgebra of X if $\mu_C(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\mu_C(t_1), \mu_C(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$. A fuzzy set $C = \{ \langle t_1, \mu_C(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$ in X is called a fuzzy ideal of X if it satisfies (i) $\mu_C(0) \geq \mu_C(t_1)$ and (ii) $\mu_C(t_1) \geq \min\{\mu_C(t_1 * t_2), \mu_A(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$.

Definition 2.8 [33] An IVFS B over X is an object of the form $B = \{ \langle t_1, \mu_B(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$ Where $\mu_B(t_1): X \rightarrow D[0:1]$, Where $D[0,1]$ is the collection of all subintervals of $[0,1]$. The interval $\mu_B(t_1)$ shows the interval of the degree of membership of the element t_1 to the set B , Where $\mu_B(t_1) = \{ \mu_{LB}(t_1), \mu_{UB}(t_1) \}, \forall t_1 \in X$.

Definition 2.9 [16] A interval valued fuzzy set $C = \{ \langle t_1, \mu_C(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$ is called a interval valued fuzzy subalgebra of X if it satisfies $\mu_C(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{\mu_C(t_1), \mu_C(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$.

Definition 2.10 [15] A pair $\tilde{P}_k = (A, \Lambda)$ is called NCS where $A = \{ \langle t_1; A_T(t_1), A_I(t_1), A_F(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$ is an INS in Y and $\Lambda = \{ \langle t_1; \lambda_T(t_1), \lambda_I(t_1), \lambda_F(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \}$ is a neutrosophic set in Y .

Definition 2.11 [26] Let $C = \{ \langle t_1, \kappa(t_1), \sigma(t_1) \rangle \}$ be a cubic set, where $\kappa(t_1)$ is an interval-valued fuzzy set in X , $\sigma(t_1)$ is a fuzzy set in X . Then C is cubic subalgebra under binary operation $*$ if following axioms are satisfied:

- C1: $\kappa(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{\kappa(t_1), \kappa(t_2)\}$,
- C2: $\sigma(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma(t_1), \sigma(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$.

Definition 2.12 [9] Suppose X be a nonempty set. A neutrosophic cubic set in X is pair $\mathcal{C} = (\kappa, \sigma)$ where $\kappa = \{ \langle t_1; \kappa_E(t_1), \kappa_I(t_1), \kappa_N(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$ is an interval neutrosophic set in X and $\sigma = \{ \langle t_1; \sigma_E(t_1), \sigma_I(t_1), \sigma_N(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$ is a neutrosophic set in X .

Definition 2.13 [9] For any $\mathcal{C}_i = (\kappa_i, \sigma_i)$ where

- $\kappa_i = \{ \langle t_1; \kappa_{iE}(t_1), \kappa_{iI}(t_1), \kappa_{iN}(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$,
- $\sigma_i = \{ \langle t_1; \sigma_{iE}(t_1), \sigma_{iI}(t_1), \sigma_{iN}(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$ for $i \in k$, P-union, P-inersection, R-un -ion and R-intersection are defined respectively by

P-union $\bigcup_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i = (\bigcup_{i \in k} \kappa_i, \bigvee_{i \in k} \sigma_i)$, **P-intersection** $\bigcap_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i = (\bigcap_{i \in k} \kappa_i, \bigwedge_{i \in k} \sigma_i)$,

R-union $\bigcup_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i = (\bigcup_{i \in k} \kappa_i, \bigwedge_{i \in k} \sigma_i)$, **R-intersection:** $\bigcap_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i = (\bigcap_{i \in k} \kappa_i, \bigvee_{i \in k} \sigma_i)$,

where

$$\bigcup_{i \in k} \kappa_i = \{ \langle t_1; (\bigcup_{i \in k} \kappa_{iE})(t_1), (\bigcup_{i \in k} \kappa_{iI})(t_1), (\bigcup_{i \in k} \kappa_{iN})(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \},$$

$$\bigvee_{i \in k} \sigma_i = \{ \langle t_1; (\bigvee_{i \in k} \sigma_{iE})(t_1), (\bigvee_{i \in k} \sigma_{iI})(t_1), (\bigvee_{i \in k} \sigma_{iN})(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \},$$

$$\bigcap_{i \in k} \kappa_i = \{ \langle t_1; (\bigcap_{i \in k} \kappa_{iE})(t_1), (\bigcap_{i \in k} \kappa_{iI})(t_1), (\bigcap_{i \in k} \kappa_{iN})(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \},$$

$$\bigwedge_{i \in k} \sigma_i = \{ \langle t_1; (\bigwedge_{i \in k} \sigma_{iE})(t_1), (\bigwedge_{i \in k} \sigma_{iI})(t_1), (\bigwedge_{i \in k} \sigma_{iN})(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \},$$

Definition 2.14 [36] Let $C = (\mu_C, \nu_C)$ be an IFS in BF-algebra X and $t \in [0,1]$, then the IFS C^t is called the t -intuitionistic fuzzy subset of X w.r.t C and is defined as $C^t = \{ \langle t_1, \mu_{C^t}(t_1), \nu_{C^t}(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in Y \} = \langle \mu_{C^t}, \nu_{C^t} \rangle$ where $\mu_{C^t}(t_1) = \min\{\mu_C(t_1), t\}$ and $\nu_{C^t}(t_1) = \max\{\nu_C(t_1), 1 - t\} \forall t_1 \in X$.

Definition 2.15 [36] Let $B^t = (\mu_{B^t}, \nu_{B^t})$ be a t -intuitionistic fuzzy subset of BF-algebra X and $t \in [0,1]$ then B^t is called t -intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra of X if it fulfills these axioms.

- (i) $\mu_{B^t}(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\mu_{B^t}(t_1), \mu_{B^t}(t_2)\}$,
- (ii) $\nu_{B^t}(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\nu_{B^t}(t_1), \nu_{B^t}(t_2)\}, \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$.

3 t-Neutrosophic Cubic Subalgebra of BF-algebra

Let $\mathcal{C} = (\kappa_C, \sigma_C)$ be a neutrosophic cubic set [NCS] of BF-algebra X , then the NCS \mathcal{C} is called the t -neutrosophic cubic set (**t-NCS**) of X w.r.t \mathcal{C} and is defined as $\mathcal{C}^t = \{ \langle t_1, \hat{\kappa}^t(t_1), \sigma^t(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \} = \langle \hat{\kappa}^t, \sigma^t \rangle$ such that $\hat{\kappa}^t(t_1) = \{ \langle \hat{\kappa}_E^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_I^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_N^t(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$ and $\sigma^t(t_1) = \{ \langle \sigma_E^t(t_1), \sigma_I^t(t_1), \sigma_N^t(t_1) \rangle \mid t_1 \in X \}$ with two independent components where $\hat{\kappa}^t(t_1) = \{ \min(\hat{\kappa}_E(t_1), t), \min(\hat{\kappa}_I(t_1), t'), \min(\hat{\kappa}_N(t_1), 2 - t - t') \}, \sigma^t(t_1) = \{ \max(\sigma_E(t_1), t), \max(\sigma_I(t_1), t'), \max(\sigma_N(t_1), 2 - t - t') \}$ and $\forall t, t', 2 - t - t' \in [0,1]$ and now concept of cubic subalgebra can be extended to t -NCSU.

Definition 3.1 Let $\mathcal{C} = (\hat{\kappa}, \sigma)$ be a cubic set, where X is subalgebra. Then \mathcal{C} is t -NCSU under binary operation $*$ if it satisfies the following conditions:

N1:

$$\hat{\kappa}_E^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\hat{\kappa}_E^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_E^t(t_2)\},$$

$$\hat{\kappa}_I^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\hat{\kappa}_I^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_I^t(t_2)\},$$

$$\hat{\kappa}_N^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\hat{\kappa}_N^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_N^t(t_2)\},$$

N2:

$$\sigma_E^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma_E^t(t_1), \sigma_E^t(t_2)\}$$

$$\sigma_I^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma_I^t(t_1), \sigma_I^t(t_2)\}$$

$$\sigma_N^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma_N^t(t_1), \sigma_N^t(t_2)\}.$$

Where **E** means existenceship/membership value, **I** means indeterminacy existenceship/membership value and **N** means non existenceship/membership value. For our convenience we introduce new notation for t-neutrosophic cubic set as

$$\mathcal{C} = (\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{E,I,N}^t, \sigma_{E,I,N}^t) = \{(t_1, \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{E,I,N}^t(t_1), \sigma_{E,I,N}^t(t_1))\} = \{(t_1, \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1))\}$$

and for conditions N1, N2 as

$$N1: \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\},$$

$$N2: \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \text{max}\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}.$$

Example 3.2 Let $X = \{0, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5\}$ be a BF-algebra with the following Cayley table.

*	0	t ₁	t ₂	t ₃	t ₄	t ₅
0	0	t ₅	t ₄	t ₃	t ₂	t ₁
t ₁	t ₁	0	t ₅	t ₄	t ₃	t ₂
t ₂	t ₂	t ₁	0	t ₅	t ₄	t ₃
t ₃	t ₃	t ₂	t ₁	0	t ₅	t ₄
t ₄	t ₄	t ₃	t ₂	t ₁	0	t ₅
t ₅	t ₅	t ₄	t ₃	t ₂	t ₁	0

A t-neutrosophic cubic set $\mathcal{C} = (\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ of X is defined by

	0	t ₁	t ₂	t ₃	t ₄	t ₅
$\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_E^t$	[0.7,0.9]	[0.6,0.8]	[0.7,0.9]	[0.6,0.8]	[0.7,0.9]	[0.6,0.8]
$\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_I^t$	[0.3,0.2]	[0.2,0.1]	[0.3,0.2]	[0.2,0.1]	[0.3,0.2]	[0.2,0.1]
$\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_N^t$	[0.2,0.4]	[0.1,0.4]	[0.2,0.4]	[0.1,0.4]	[0.2,0.4]	[0.1,0.4]

	0	t ₁	t ₂	t ₃	t ₄	t ₅
σ_E^t	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3
σ_I^t	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.5
σ_N^t	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.6

Both the conditions of definition are satisfied by the set \mathcal{C} . Thus $\mathcal{C} = (\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is a t-NCSU of X .

Proposition 3.3 Let $\mathcal{C} = \{(t_1, \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1))\}$ is a t-NCSU of X , then $\forall t_1 \in X, \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \geq \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(0)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$. Thus, $\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(0)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(0)$ are the upper bound and lower bound of $\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ respectively.

Proof. $\forall t_1 \in X$, we have $\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(0) = \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)\} = \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \Rightarrow \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(0) \geq \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_1) \leq \text{max}\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)\} = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \Rightarrow \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$.

Theorem 3.4 Let $\mathcal{C}=\{(t_1, \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1))\}$ be a t-NCSU of X . If there exists a sequence $\{(t_1)_n\}$ of X such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t((t_1)_n) = [1,1]$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_{\Xi}^t((t_1)_n) = 0$. Then $\widehat{\mathcal{R}}_{\Xi}^t(0) = [1,1]$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) = 0$.

Proof. Using above proposition, $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0) \geq \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \forall t_1 \in X, \therefore \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0) \geq \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t((t_1)_n)$ for $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Consider, $[1,1] \geq \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t((t_1)_n) = [1,1]$. Hence $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0) = [1,1]$.

Again, using proposition, $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \forall t_1 \in X, \therefore \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t((t_1)_n)$ for $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$. Consider, $0 \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_{\Xi}^t((t_1)_n) = 0$. Hence $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) = 0$.

Theorem 3.5 The R-intersection of any set of t-NCSU of X is t-NCSU of X.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}_i^t = \{(t_1, (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}) | t_1 \in X\}$ where $i \in k$, is family of sets of t-NCSU of X and $t_1, t_2 \in X$ and $t \in [0,1]$ Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) &= \text{rinf}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1 * t_2) \\ &\geq \text{rinf}\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\text{rinf}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \text{rinf}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{(\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\} \\ &\Rightarrow (\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{(\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) &= \text{sup}(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1 * t_2) \\ &\leq \text{sup}\{\text{max}\{(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} \\ &= \text{max}\{\text{sup}(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \text{sup}(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\} \\ &= \text{max}\{(\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\} \\ &\Rightarrow (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) \leq \text{max}\{(\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\}, \end{aligned}$$

which show that R-intersection of \mathcal{C}_i^t is t-NCSU of X.

Remark 3.6 The R-union, P-intersection and P-union of t-NCSU need not to be a t-NCSU which is explained through example.

let $X = \{0, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5\}$ be a BF-algebra with the following Caley table.

*	0	t ₁	t ₂	t ₃	t ₄	t ₅
0	0	t ₂	t ₁	t ₃	t ₄	t ₅
t ₁	t ₁	0	t ₂	t ₅	t ₃	t ₄
t ₂	t ₂	t ₁	0	t ₄	t ₅	t ₃
t ₃	t ₃	t ₄	t ₅	0	t ₁	t ₂
t ₄	t ₄	t ₅	t ₃	t ₂	0	t ₁
t ₅	t ₅	t ₃	t ₄	t ₁	t ₂	0

Let $\mathcal{C}_1^t = ((\hat{\kappa}_1^t)_{\Xi}^1, (\sigma_1^t)_{\Xi}^1)$ and $\mathcal{C}_2^t = ((\hat{\kappa}_2^t)_{\Xi}^2, (\sigma_2^t)_{\Xi}^2)$ are t-neutrosophic cubic sets of X which are defined by

	0	t ₁	t ₂	t ₃	t ₄	t ₅
$\hat{\kappa}_1^t E$	[0.4,0.5]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.4,0.5]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.2,0.3]
$\hat{\kappa}_1^t I$	[0.6,0.7]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.6,0.7]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]
$\hat{\kappa}_1^t N$	[0.7,0.8]	[0.4,0.5]	[0.4,0.5]	[0.7,0.8]	[0.4,0.5]	[0.4,0.5]
$\hat{\kappa}_2^t E$	[0.7,0.8]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.7,0.8]	[0.3,0.4]
$\hat{\kappa}_2^t I$	[0.8,0.7]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.2,0.3]	[0.8,0.7]	[0.2,0.3]
$\hat{\kappa}_2^t N$	[0.7,0.6]	[0.2,0.4]	[0.2,0.4]	[0.2,0.4]	[0.7,0.6]	[0.2,0.4]

	0	t ₁	t ₂	t ₃	t ₄	t ₅
$\sigma_1^t E$	0.2	0.9	0.9	0.2	0.9	0.9
$\sigma_1^t I$	0.3	0.8	0.8	0.3	0.8	0.8
$\sigma_1^t N$	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.7
$\sigma_2^t E$	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.3	0.6
$\sigma_2^t I$	0.4	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.4	0.8
$\sigma_2^t N$	0.5	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.3	0.8

$$(U (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E)(a_3 * a_4) = ([0.3,0.4], [0.3,0.4], [0.4,0.5])_E \not\geq ([0.7,0.8], [0.6,0.7], [0.5,0.6])_E =$$

$$\text{rmin}\{(U (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E)(a_3), (U (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E)(a_4)\} \text{ and } (\wedge (\sigma^t)_E)(a_3 * a_4) = (0.5,0.6,0.7)_E \not\leq (0.3,0.4,0.5)_E = \text{max}\{(\wedge$$

$$(\sigma^t)_E)(a_3), (\wedge (\sigma^t)_E)(a_4)\}.$$

Theorem 3.7. Let $C_i^t = \{(t_1, (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E, (\sigma^t)_E) | t_1 \in X\}$ be a collection of sets of t-NCSU of X, where $i \in k$ and $t \in [0,1]$. If $\inf\{\text{max}\{(\sigma^t)_E(t_1), (\sigma^t)_E(t_1)\}\} = \text{max}\{\inf(\sigma^t)_E(t_1)$
 $, \inf(\sigma^t)_E(t_1)\} \forall t_1 \in X$, then the P-intersection of C_i^t is also a t-NCSU of X.

Proof. Suppose that $C_i^t = \{(t_1, (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E, (\sigma^t)_E) | t_1 \in X\}$ where $i \in k$, be a collection of sets of t-NCSU of X such that $\inf\{\text{max}\{(\sigma^t)_E(t_1), (\sigma^t)_E(t_1)\}\} = \text{max}\{\inf(\sigma^t)_E(t_1), \inf(\sigma^t)_E(t_1)\} \forall a \in X$. Then for $t_1, t_2 \in X$ and $t \in [0,1]$. Then

$$(\cap (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E)(t_1 * t_2) = \text{rinf}\{(\hat{\kappa}^t)_E(t_1 * t_2)\}$$

$$\geq \text{rinf}\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}^t)_E(t_1), (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E(t_2)\}\}$$

$$= \text{rmin}\{\text{rinf}(\hat{\kappa}^t)_E(t_1), \text{rinf}(\hat{\kappa}^t)_E(t_2)\}$$

$$= \text{rmin}\{(\cap (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E)(t_1), (\cap (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E)(t_2)\}$$

$$\Rightarrow (\cap (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E)(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{(\cap (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E)(t_1), (\cap (\hat{\kappa}^t)_E)(t_2)\}$$

and

$$(\wedge (\sigma^t)_E)(t_1 * t_2) = \inf(\sigma^t)_E(t_1 * t_2)$$

$$\leq \inf\{\text{max}\{(\sigma^t)_E(t_1), (\sigma^t)_E(t_2)\}\}$$

$$= \text{max}\{\inf(\sigma^t)_E(t_1), \inf(\sigma^t)_E(t_2)\}$$

$$= \text{max}\{(\wedge (\sigma^t)_E)(t_1), (\wedge (\sigma^t)_E)(t_2)\}$$

$$\Rightarrow (\wedge (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{(\wedge (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\wedge (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\},$$

which show that P-intersection of \mathcal{C}_i^t is t-NCSU of X.

Theorem 3.8. Let $\mathcal{C}_i^t = \{(t_1, (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}) | t_1 \in X\}$ where $i \in k$, be a collection of sets of t-NCSU of X. If $\sup\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\sup(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \sup(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}$ and $\inf\{\max\{(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \inf(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}$, $\forall t_1 \in X$. Then P -union of \mathcal{C}_i^t is t-NCSU of X.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}_i^t = \{(t_1, (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}) | t_1 \in X\}$ where $i \in k$, be a collection of sets of t-NCSU of X such that $\sup\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\sup(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \sup(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}$

$\forall t_1 \in X$. Then for $t_1, t_2 \in X$, and $t \in [0,1]$.

$$\begin{aligned} (\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) &= \text{rsup}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1 * t_2) \\ &\geq \text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \text{rsup}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{(\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\} \\ &\Rightarrow (\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{(\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) &= \sup(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1 * t_2) \\ &\leq \sup\{\max\{(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\sup(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \sup(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\} \\ &= \max\{(\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\} \\ &\Rightarrow (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{(\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\}, \end{aligned}$$

which show that P-union of \mathcal{C}_i^t is t-NCSU of X.

Theorem 3.9 Let $\mathcal{C}_i^t = \{(t_1, (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}) | t_1 \in X\}$ where $i \in k$, be a collection of sets of t-NCSU of X. If $\inf\{\max\{(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \inf(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}$ and $\sup\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\sup(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \sup(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\} \forall t_1 \in X$ and $t \in [0,1]$. Then R-union of \mathcal{C}_i^t is a t-NCSU of X.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}_i^t = \{(t_1, (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}) | t_1 \in X\}$ where $i \in k$, and $t \in [0,1]$ be collection of sets of t-NCSU of X such that $\inf\{\max\{(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \inf(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}$ and $\sup\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}$

$\{\sup(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \sup(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\} \forall t_1 \in X$. Then for $t_1, t_2 \in X$ and $t \in [0,1]$

$$\begin{aligned} (\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) &= \text{rsup}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1 * t_2) \\ &\geq \text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \text{rsup}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\} \\ &= \text{rmin}\{(\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\} \\ &\Rightarrow (\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{(\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1), (\cup (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (\wedge (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})(t_1 * t_2) &= \inf(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1 * t_2) \\ &\leq \inf\{\max\{(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \max\{\inf(\sigma_i^t)_\Xi(t_1), \inf(\sigma_i^t)_\Xi(t_2)\} \\
 &= \max\{(\wedge (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1), (\wedge (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_2)\} \\
 &\Rightarrow (\wedge (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{(\wedge (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1), (\wedge (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_2)\},
 \end{aligned}$$

which show that R-union of C_i^t is t-NCSU of X.

Theorem 3.10 If t-neutrosophic cubic set $C^t = (\hat{K}_\Xi^t, \sigma_\Xi^t)$ of X is subalgebra, then $\forall t_1 \in X, \hat{K}_\Xi^t(0 * t_1) \geq \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1)$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(0 * t_1) \leq \sigma_\Xi^t(t_1)$.

Proof. For all $t_1 \in X$, $\hat{K}_\Xi^t(0 * t_1) \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(0), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1)\} = \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1)\} \geq \min\{\min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1)\}, \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1)\} = \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1)$ and similarly $\sigma_\Xi^t(0 * t_1) \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(0), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_1)\} = \sigma_\Xi^t(t_1)$.

Theorem 3.11 If t-neutrosophic cubic set $C^t = (\hat{K}_\Xi^t, \sigma_\Xi^t)$ of X is subalgebra then $C^t(t_1 * t_2) = C^t(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2))) \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$.

Proof. Let X be a BF-algebra and $t_1, t_2 \in X$. Then we know by above lemma that $t_2 = 0 * (0 * t_2)$. Hence $\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2) = \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2)))$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2) = \sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2)))$. Therefore, $C_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2) = C_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2)))$.

Theorem 3.12 If t-neutrosophic cubic set $C^t = (\hat{K}_\Xi^t, \sigma_\Xi^t)$ of X is t-NCSU, then $\forall t_1, t_2 \in X, \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\}$.

Proof. Let $t_1, t_2 \in X$. Then we have $\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(0 * t_2)\} \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1), \sigma_\Xi^t(0 * t_2)\} \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\}$ by definition and proposition.

Theorem 3.13 If a t-neutrosophic cubic set $C^t = (\hat{K}_\Xi^t, \sigma_\Xi^t)$ of X satisfies the following conditions, then C^t refers to a t-NCSU of X:

1. $\hat{K}_\Xi^t(0 * t_1) \geq \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1)$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(0 * t_1) \leq \sigma_\Xi^t(t_1) \forall t_1 \in X$
2. $\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * t_2)) \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\}, \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$ and $t \in [0,1]$.

Proof. Assume that the t-neutrosophic cubic set $C^t = (\hat{K}_\Xi^t, \sigma_\Xi^t)$ of X satisfies the above conditions (1 and 2). Then by lemma, we have $\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2) = \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2))) \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(0 * t_2)\} \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2) = \sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * (0 * (0 * t_2))) \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1), \sigma_\Xi^t(0 * t_2)\} \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\} \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$. Hence C^t is t-NCSU of X.

Theorem 3.14 A t-neutrosophic cubic set $C^t = (\hat{K}_\Xi^t, \sigma_\Xi^t)$ of X is t-NCSU of X $\Leftrightarrow \hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}, \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}$ and σ_Ξ^t are fuzzy subalgebra of X.

Proof. Let $\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}, \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}$ and σ_Ξ^t are fuzzy subalgebra of X and $t_1, t_2 \in X$ and $t \in [0,1]$. Then $\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_2)\}, \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\}$. Now, $\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2) = [\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_1 * t_2), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_1 * t_2)] \geq [\min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_2)\}, \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_2)\}] \geq \min\{[\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_2)], [\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_2), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_1)]\} = \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_2)\}$. Therefore, C^t is t-NCSU of X. Conversely, assume that C^t is a t-NCSU of X. For any $t_1, t_2 \in X$, $[\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_1 * t_2), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_1 * t_2)] = \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^t(t_2)\} = \min\{[\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_1)], [\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_2), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_2)]\} = [\min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_2)\}, \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_2)\}]$. Thus, $\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}(t_2)\}$, $\hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_1), \hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\}$. Hence $\hat{K}_\Xi^{t+}, \hat{K}_\Xi^{t-}$ and σ_Ξ^t are fuzzy subalgebra of X.

Theorem 3.15 Let $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ be a t-NCSU of X and $n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ (the set of positive integer). Then

1. $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_n t_1 * t_1) \geq \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ for $n \in \mathbb{O}$,
2. $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_n t_1 * t_1) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ for $n \in \mathbb{O}$,
3. $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_n t_1 * t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ for $n \in \mathbb{E}$,
4. $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_n t_1 * t_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ for $n \in \mathbb{E}$.

Proof. Let $t_1 \in X$ and n is odd. Then $n = 2q - 1$ for some positive integer q . We prove the theorem by induction. Now $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0) \geq \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$. Suppose that $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_{2q-1} t_1 * t_1) \geq \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_{2q-1} t_1 * t_1) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$. Then by assumption, $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_{2(q+1)-1} t_1 * t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_{2q+1} t_1 * t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_{2q-1} t_1 * (t_1 * (t_1 * t_1))) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_{2q-1} t_1 * t_1) \geq \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_{2(q+1)-1} t_1 * t_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_{2q+1} t_1 * t_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_{2q-1} t_1 * (t_1 * (t_1 * t_1))) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\mathcal{J}_{2q-1} t_1 * t_1) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$, which prove (1) and (2), similarly we can prove the remaining cases (3) and (4).

Theorem 3.16 The sets denoted by $I_{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t}$ and $I_{\sigma_{\Xi}^t}$ are also subalgebras of X , which are defined as: $I_{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t} = \{t_1 \in X | \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0)\}$, $I_{\sigma_{\Xi}^t} = \{t_1 \in X | \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0)\}$. Let $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ be a t-NCSU of X . Then the sets $I_{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t}$ and $I_{\sigma_{\Xi}^t}$ are subalgebras of X .

Proof. Let $t_1, t_2 \in I_{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t}$. Then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)$ and $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0)$. By using Proposition 3.3, we know that $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0)$ or equivalently $t_1 * t_2 \in I_{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t}$. Again let $t_1, t_2 \in I_{\sigma_{\Xi}^t}$. Then $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0)$. Again by using Proposition 3.3, we know that $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0)$ or equivalently $t_1 * t_2 \in I_{\sigma_{\Xi}^t}$. Hence the sets $I_{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t}$ and $I_{\sigma_{\Xi}^t}$ are subalgebras of X .

Theorem 3.17 Let A be a nonempty subset of X and $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ be a t-neutrosophic cubic set of X defined by

$$\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \begin{cases} [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}], & \text{if } t_1 \in A \\ [v_{\Xi_1}, v_{\Xi_2}], & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \begin{cases} \phi_{\Xi}, & \text{if } t_1 \in A \\ \delta_{\Xi}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

, $\forall [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}], [v_{\Xi_1}, v_{\Xi_2}] \in D[0,1]$ and $\phi_{\Xi}, \delta_{\Xi} \in [0,1]$ with $[\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}] \geq [v_{\Xi_1}, v_{\Xi_2}]$ and $\phi_{\Xi} \leq \delta_{\Xi}$. Then \mathcal{C}^t is a t-NCSU of $X \Leftrightarrow A$ is a subalgebra of X . Moreover, $I_{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t} = A = I_{\sigma_{\Xi}^t}$

Proof. Let \mathcal{C}^t be a t-NCSU of X and $t_1, t_2 \in X$ such that $t_1, t_2 \in A$. Then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \min\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} = \min\{[\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}], [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}]\} = [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}]$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} = \max\{\phi_{\Xi}, \phi_{\Xi}\} = \phi_{\Xi}$. Therefore $t_1 * t_2 \in A$. Hence A is a subalgebra of X .

Conversely, suppose that A is a subalgebra of X and $t_1, t_2 \in X$. Consider two cases.

Case 1: If $t_1, t_2 \in A$ then $t_1 * t_2 \in A$, thus $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) = [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}] = \min\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) = \phi_{\Xi} = \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$.

Case 2: If $t_1 \notin A$ or $t_2 \notin A$, then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq [v_{\Xi_1}, v_{\Xi_2}] = \min\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \delta_{\Xi} = \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$. Hence \mathcal{C}^t is a t-NCSU of X .

Now, $I_{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t} = \{t_1 \in X, \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0)\} = \{t_1 \in X, \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = [\alpha_{\Xi_1}, \alpha_{\Xi_2}]\} = A$ and $I_{\sigma_{\Xi}^t} = \{t_1 \in X, \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0)\} = \{t_1 \in X, \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \gamma_{\Xi}\} = A$.

Definition 3.18 Let $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ be a t-neutrosophic cubic set of X . For $[s_{E_1}, s_{E_2}], [s_{I_1}, s_{I_2}], [s_{N_1}, s_{N_2}] \in D[0,1]$ and $t_{E_1}, t_{I_1}, t_{N_1} \in [0,1]$, the set $U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t | ([s_{E_1}, s_{E_2}], [s_{I_1}, s_{I_2}], [s_{N_1}, s_{N_2}])) = \{t_1 \in X | \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \geq [s_{E_1}, s_{E_2}], \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \geq [s_{I_1}, s_{I_2}], \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \geq [s_{N_1}, s_{N_2}]\}$ is called upper $([s_{E_1}, s_{E_2}], [s_{I_1}, s_{I_2}], [s_{N_1}, s_{N_2}])$ -level of \mathcal{C}^t and $L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t | (t_{E_1}, t_{I_1}, t_{N_1})) = \{t_1 \in X | \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \leq t_{E_1}, \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \leq t_{I_1}, \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \leq t_{N_1}\}$ is called lower $(t_{E_1}, t_{I_1}, t_{N_1})$ -level of \mathcal{C}^t .

For comfort, we introduce the new notions for upper level and lower level of \mathcal{C}^t as, $U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])=\{t_1 \in X|\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \geq [s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}]\}$ is called upper $([s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$ -level of \mathcal{C}^t and $L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})=\{t_1 \in X|\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \leq t_{\Xi_1}\}$ is called lower t_{Ξ_1} -level of \mathcal{C}^t .

Theorem 3.19 If $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is t-NCSU of X , then the upper $[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}]$ -level and lower t_{Ξ_1} -level of \mathcal{C}^t are subalgebras of X .

Proof. Let $t_1, t_2 \in U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$. Then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \geq [s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}]$ and $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2) \geq [s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}]$. It follows that $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} \geq [s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}] \Rightarrow t_1 * t_2 \in U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$. Hence, $U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$ is a subalgebra of X . Let $t_1, t_2 \in L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$. Then $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \leq t_{\Xi_1}$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2) \leq t_{\Xi_1}$. It follows that $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} \leq t_{\Xi_1} \Rightarrow t_1 * t_2 \in L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$. Hence $L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$ is a subalgebra of X .

Corollary 3.20 Let $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is t-NCSU of X . Then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t([s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}]; t_{\Xi_1}) = U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}]) \cap L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1}) = \{t_1 \in X|\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \geq [s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}], \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \leq t_{\Xi_1}\}$ is a subalgebra of X .

Proof. We can prove it by using above proved Theorem. The converse of above corollary is not valid.

Theorem 3.21 Every subalgebra of X can be realized as both the upper $[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}]$ -level and lower t_{Ξ_1} -level of some t-NCSU of X .

Proof. Let \mathcal{A}^t be a t-NCSU of X , and t-neutrosophic cubic set \mathcal{C}^t on X is defined by

$$\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t = \begin{pmatrix} [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}] & \text{if } t_1 \in \mathcal{A}^t \\ [0,0] & \text{otherwise} \end{pmatrix}, \sigma_{\Xi}^t = \begin{pmatrix} v_{\Xi_1} & \text{if } t_1 \in \mathcal{A}^t \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{pmatrix}$$

$\forall [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}] \in D[0,1]$ and $v_{\Xi_1} \in [0,1]$. We investigate the following cases.

Case 1 If $\forall t_1, t_2 \in \mathcal{A}^t$ then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}]$, $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = v_{\Xi_1}$ and $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}]$, $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = v_{\Xi_1}$. Thus $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) = [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}] = \text{rmin}\{[\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}], [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}]\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) = v_{\Xi_1} = \max\{v_{\Xi_1}, v_{\Xi_1}\} = \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$.

Case 2 If $t_1 \in \mathcal{A}^t$ and $t_2 \notin \mathcal{A}^t$, then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}]$, $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = v_{\Xi_1}$ and $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = [0,0]$, $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = 1$. Thus $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq [0,0] = \text{rmin}\{[\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}], [0,0]\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq 1 = \max\{v_{\Xi_1}, 1\} = \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$.

Case 3 If $t_1 \notin \mathcal{A}^t$ and $t_2 \in \mathcal{A}^t$, then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = [0,0]$, $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = 1$ and $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}]$, $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = v_{\Xi_1}$. Thus $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq [0,0] = \text{rmin}\{[0,0], [\mu_{\Xi_1}, \mu_{\Xi_2}]\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq 1 = \max\{1, v_{\Xi_1}\} = \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$.

Case 4 If $t_1 \notin \mathcal{A}^t$ and $t_2 \notin \mathcal{A}^t$, then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = [0,0]$, $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = 1$ and $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = [0,0]$, $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = 1$. Thus $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq [0,0] = \text{rmin}\{[0,0], [0,0]\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq 1 = \max\{1, 1\} = \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$. Therefore, \mathcal{C}^t is a t-NCSU of X .

Theorem 3.22 Let \mathcal{A}^t be a subset of X and \mathcal{C}^t be a t-neutrosophic cubic set on X which is given in the proof of above theorem. If \mathcal{C}^t is realized as lower level subalgebra and upper level subalgebra of some t-NCSU of X , then \mathcal{B}^t is a t-neutrosophic cubic one of X .

Proof. Let \mathcal{C}^t be a t-NCSU of X , and $t_1, t_2 \in \mathcal{C}^t$. Then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = [\alpha_{\Xi_1}, \alpha_{\Xi_2}]$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = \beta_{\Xi_1}$. Thus $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{[\alpha_{\Xi_1}, \alpha_{\Xi_2}], [\alpha_{\Xi_1}, \alpha_{\Xi_2}]\} = [\alpha_{\Xi_1}, \alpha_{\Xi_2}]$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} = \max\{\beta_{\Xi_1}, \beta_{\Xi_1}\} = \beta_{\Xi_1} \Rightarrow t_1 * t_2 \in \mathcal{A}^t$. Hence proof is completed.

4 Image and Pre-image of t-Neutrosophic Cubic Subalgebra

In this section, homomorphism of t-neutrosophic cubic subalgebra is defined and some results are studied.

Suppose Γ be a mapping from X into Y and $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ be a t-neutrosophic cubic set in X . Then the inverse-image of \mathcal{C}^t is defined as $\Gamma^{-1}(\mathcal{C}^t) = \{(t_1, \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t), \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)) | t_1 \in X\}$ and $\Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1))$ and $\Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1))$. It can be shown that $\Gamma^{-1}(\mathcal{C}^t)$ is a t-neutrosophic cubic set.

Theorem 4.1 Suppose that $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism of BF-algebra. If $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is a t-NCSU of Y , then the pre-image $\Gamma^{-1}(\mathcal{C}^t) = \{(t_1, \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t), \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)) | t_1 \in X\}$ of \mathcal{C}^t under Γ is a t-NCSU of X .

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is a t-NCSU of Y and $t_1, t_2 \in X$. Then $\Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_1 * t_2) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1 * t_2)) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1) * \Gamma(t_2)) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1)), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_2))\} = \text{rmin}\{\Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_1), \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_2)\}$ and $\Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_1 * t_2) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1 * t_2)) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1) * \Gamma(t_2)) \leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1)), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_2))\} = \max\{\Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_1), \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_2)\}$. $\therefore \Gamma^{-1}(\mathcal{C}^t) = \{(t_1, \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t), \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)) | t_1 \in X\}$ is t-NCSU of X .

Theorem 4.2 Consider $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism of BF-algebra and $\mathcal{C}_j^t = ((\hat{\kappa}_j^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_j^t)_{\Xi})$ be a t-NCSU of Y , where $j \in k$. If $\inf\{\max\{(\sigma_j^t)_{\Xi}(t_2), (\sigma_{j'}^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf\{(\sigma_j^t)_{\Xi}(t_2), \inf\{(\sigma_{j'}^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\}, \forall t_2 \in Y$. Then $\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{j \in k} \mathcal{C}_j^t)$ is t-NCSU of X .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}_j^t = ((\hat{\kappa}_j^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_j^t)_{\Xi})$ be a t-NCSU of Y where $j \in k$ satisfying $\inf\{\max\{(\sigma_j^t)_{\Xi}(t_2), (\sigma_{j'}^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} = \max\{\inf\{(\sigma_j^t)_{\Xi}(t_2), \inf\{(\sigma_{j'}^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\}, \forall t_2 \in Y$. Then by Theorem 3.7 we know, $\bigcap_{j \in k} \mathcal{C}_j^t$ is a t-NCSU of Y .

Hence $\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{j \in k} \mathcal{C}_j^t)$ is t-NCSU of X .

Theorem 4.3 Let $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism of BF-algebra. Assume that $\mathcal{C}_j^t = ((\hat{\kappa}_j^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_j^t)_{\Xi})$ be a collection of sets of t-NCSU of Y where $j \in k$. If $\text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_j^t)_{\Xi}(t_2), (\hat{\kappa}_{j'}^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}\{(\hat{\kappa}_j^t)_{\Xi}(t_2), \text{rsup}\{(\hat{\kappa}_{j'}^t)_{\Xi}(t_2)\}\}, \forall (t_2), (t_2)' \in Y$. Then $\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcup_{j \in k} \mathcal{C}_j^t)$ is t-NCSU of X .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}_j^t = ((\hat{\kappa}_j^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_j^t)_{\Xi})$ be a t-NCSU of Y where $j \in k$ satisfying $\text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_j^t)_{\Xi}(t_2), (\hat{\kappa}_{j'}^t)_{\Xi}(t_2')\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}\{(\hat{\kappa}_j^t)_{\Xi}(t_2), \text{rsup}\{(\hat{\kappa}_{j'}^t)_{\Xi}(t_2')\}\} \forall t_2, t_2' \in Y$. Then by Theorem 3.8 we know, $\bigcup_{j \in k} \mathcal{C}_j^t$ is a t-NCSU of Y . Hence $\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcup_{j \in k} \mathcal{C}_j^t)$ is t-NCSU of X .

Definition 4.4 A t-neutrosophic cubic set $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ in BF-algebra X is said to have rsup-property and inf-property for any subset P of X , $\exists p_0 \in T$ such that $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(p_0) = \text{rsup}_{p_0 \in S} \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(p_0)$ and

$$\sigma_{\Xi}^t(s_0) = \inf_{t_0 \in T} \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_0) \text{ respectively.}$$

Definition 4.5 Let Γ be mapping from X to Y . If $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is neutrosophic cubic set of X , then the image of \mathcal{C}^t under Γ is denoted by $\Gamma(\mathcal{C}^t)$ and is defined as $\Gamma(\mathcal{C}^t) = \{(t_1, \Gamma_{\text{rsup}}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t), \Gamma_{\text{inf}}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)) | t_1 \in X\}$, where

$$\Gamma_{\text{rsup}}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_2) = \begin{cases} \text{rsup}_{t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2)} (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_1), & \text{if } \Gamma^{-1}(t_2) \neq \phi \\ [0,0], & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\Gamma_{\text{inf}}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_2) = \begin{cases} \inf_{t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2)} \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), & \text{if } \Gamma^{-1}(t_2) \neq \phi \\ 1, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Theorem 4.6 Suppose $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism from a BF-algebra X onto a BF-algebra Y . If $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is a t-NCSU of X , then the image $\Gamma(\mathcal{C}^t) = \{(t_1, \Gamma_{\text{rsup}}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t), \Gamma_{\text{inf}}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)) | t_1 \in X\}$ of \mathcal{A} under Γ is t-NCSU of Y .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ be a t-NCSU of X and $t_2, t_2' \in Y$. We know that $\{t_1 * t_1' | t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2) \text{ and } t_1' \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2')\} \subseteq \{t_1 \in X | t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2 * t_2')\}$. Now $\Gamma_{\text{rsup}}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_2 * t_2') = \text{rsup}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) | t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2 * t_2')\} \geq \text{rsup}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_1') | t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2) \text{ and } t_1' \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2')\} \geq \text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1')\} | t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2) \text{ and } t_1' \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2')\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) | t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2)\}, \text{rsup}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1') | t_1' \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2')\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\Gamma_{\text{rsup}}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_2),$

$\Gamma_{\text{rsup}}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_2')\}$ and $\Gamma_{\text{inf}}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_2 * t_2') = \text{inf}\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) | t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2 * t_2')\} \leq \text{inf}\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_1') | t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2) \text{ and } t_1' \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2')\} \leq \text{inf}\{\max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1')\} | t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2) \text{ and } t_1' \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2')\} = \max\{\text{inf}\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) | t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2)\}, \text{inf}\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1') | t_1' \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2')\}\} = \max\{\Gamma_{\text{inf}}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_2), \Gamma_{\text{inf}}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_2')\}$. Hence $\Gamma(\mathcal{C}^t) = \{(t_1, \Gamma_{\text{rsup}}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t), \Gamma_{\text{inf}}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)) | t_1 \in X\}$

is a t-NCSU of Y .

Theorem 4.7 Assume that $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ is a homomorphism of BF-algebra and $\mathcal{C}_i^t = \{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}\}$ is a t-NCSU of X , where $i \in k$. If $\text{inf}\{\max\{(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1')\}\} = \max\{\text{inf}(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \text{inf}(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1')\}, \forall t_1 \in X$.

Then $\Gamma(\bigcap_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i^t)$ is a t-NCSU of Y .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}_i^t = \{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}\}$ be a collection of sets of t-NCSU of X , where $i \in k$ satisfies $\text{inf}\{\max\{(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1')\}\} = \max\{\text{inf}(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \text{inf}(\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1')\} \forall t_1 \in X$. Then by above stated theorem, $\bigcap_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i^t$ is a t-NCSU of X . Hence $\Gamma(\bigcap_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i^t)$ is t-NCSU of Y .

Theorem 4.8 Suppose $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism of BF-algebra and $\mathcal{C}_i^t = \{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}\}$ be a t-NCSU of X where $i \in k$. If $\text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1')\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \text{rsup}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1')\}, \forall t_1, t_1' \in Y$. Then $\Gamma(\bigcup_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i^t)$ is also a t-NCSU of Y .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}_i^t = \{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}\}$ be a collection of sets of t-NCSU of X where $i \in k$ satisfies $\text{rsup}\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1')\}\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rsup}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1), \text{rsup}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}(t_1')\}, \forall t_1, t_1' \in X$. Then by above stated theorem we know that $\bigcup_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i^t$ is a t-NCSU of X . Hence $\Gamma(\bigcup_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i^t)$ is t-NCSU of Y .

Theorem 4.9 For a homomorphism $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ of BF-algebra, the following results hold:

1. If $\forall i \in k, \mathcal{C}_i^t$ is t-NCSU of X , then $\Gamma(\bigcap_{i \in k} \mathcal{C}_i^t)$ is t-NCSU of Y ,
2. If $\forall i \in k, \mathcal{D}_i^t$ is t-NCSU of Y , then $\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in k} \mathcal{D}_i^t)$ is t-NCSU of X .

Proof. Straightforward.

Theorem 4.10 Let Γ be an isomorphism from a BF-algebra X onto a BF-algebra Y . If \mathcal{C}^t is a t-NCSU of X . Then $\Gamma^{-1}(\Gamma(\mathcal{C}^t)) = \mathcal{C}^t$.

Proof. For any $t_1 \in X$, let $\Gamma(t_1) = t_2$. Since Γ is an isomorphism, $\Gamma^{-1}(t_2) = \{t_1\}$. Thus $\Gamma(\mathcal{C}^t)(\Gamma(t_1)) = \Gamma(\mathcal{C}^t)(t_2) = \bigcup_{t_1 \in \Gamma^{-1}(t_2)} \mathcal{C}^t(t_1) = \mathcal{C}^t(t_1)$. For any $t_2 \in Y, \Gamma$ is an isomorphism, $\Gamma^{-1}(t_2) = \{t_1\}$ so that $\Gamma(t_1) = t_2$. Thus $\Gamma^{-1}(\mathcal{C}^t)(t_1) = \mathcal{C}^t(\Gamma(t_1)) = \mathcal{C}^t(t_2)$. Hence, $\Gamma^{-1}(\Gamma(\mathcal{C}^t)) = \mathcal{C}^t$.

Corollary 4.11 Consider Γ is an Isomorphism from a BF-algebra X onto a BF-algebra Y . If \mathcal{C}^t is a t-NCSU of Y . Then $\Gamma(\Gamma^{-1}(\mathcal{C}^t)) = \mathcal{C}^t$.

Proof. Straightforward.

Corollary 4.12 Let $\Gamma|X \rightarrow X$ be an automorphism. If \mathcal{C}^t is a t-NCSU of X . Then $\Gamma(\mathcal{C}^t) = \mathcal{C}^t \Leftarrow \Gamma^{-1}(\mathcal{C}^t) = \mathcal{C}^t$.

5 t-Neutrosophic Cubic Closed Ideal of BF-algebra

In this section, t-neutrosophic cubic ideal and t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of BF-algebra are defined and investigated through related results.

Definition 5.1 A t-neutrosophic cubic set $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ of X is called a t-NCID of X if it satisfies following axioms:

- N3. $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0) \geq \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$,
- N4. $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$,
- N5. $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}$, $\forall t_1, t_2 \in X$.

Example 5.2 Consider a BF-algebra $X = \{0, t_1, t_2, t_3\}$ and binary operation * is defined on X as

*	0	t_1	t_2	t_3
	0	t_1	t_2	t_3
t_1	t_1	0	t_3	t_2
t_2	t_2	t_3	0	t_1
t_3	t_3	t_2	t_1	0

Let $\mathcal{C}^t = \{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t\}$ be a t-neutrosophic cubic set in X is defined as,

	0	t_1	t_2	t_3
$\hat{\kappa}_{E}^t$	[1,1]	[0.8,0.7]	[1,1]	[0.4,0.6]
$\hat{\kappa}_{I}^t$	[0.8,0.8]	[0.5,0.7]	[0.8,0.8]	[0.6,0.4]
$\hat{\kappa}_{N}^t$	[0.7,0.8]	[0.4,0.5]	[0.7,0.8]	[0.8,0.4]

and

	0	t_1	t_2	t_3
σ_{E}^t	0	0.7	0	0.6
σ_{I}^t	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.6
σ_{N}^t	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.4

Then it can be easy verify that \mathcal{C}^t satisfies the conditions N3, N4 and N5. Hence \mathcal{C}^t is t-NCID of X.

Definition 5.3 Let $\mathcal{C}^t = \{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t\}$ be a t-neutrosophic cubic set X then it is called t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of X if it satisfies N4, N5 and N6. $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0 * t_1) \geq \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(0 * t_1) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$, $\forall t_1 \in X$.

Example 5.4 Let $X = \{0, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5\}$ be a BF-algebra as in Example 3.2 and $\mathcal{C}^t = \{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t\}$ be a t-neutrosophic cubic set in X is defined as

	0	t_1	t_2	t_3	t_4	t_5
$\hat{\kappa}_{E}^t$	[0.4,0.7]	[0.3,0.6]	[0.3,0.6]	[0.2,0.4]	[0.2,0.4]	[0.2,0.4]
$\hat{\kappa}_{I}^t$	[0.5,0.8]	[0.4,0.7]	[0.4,0.7]	[0.3,0.6]	[0.3,0.6]	[0.3,0.6]
$\hat{\kappa}_{N}^t$	[0.6,0.9]	[0.5,0.8]	[0.5,0.8]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]

	0	t_1	t_2	t_3	t_4	t_5
σ^t_E	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.8
σ^t_I	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.7	0.7
σ^t_N	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.9	0.9	0.9

By calculations it is clear that \mathcal{C}^t is a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of X.

Proposition 5.5 Every t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal is a t-NCID.

Proof The converse of proposition 5.5 is not true in general as shown in the given example.

Example 5.6 Let $X = \{0, t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4, t_5\}$ be a BF-algebra as in Example 3.2 and $\mathcal{C}^t = \{\hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}, \sigma^t_{\Xi}\}$ be a t-neutrosophic cubic set in X is defined as

	0	t_1	t_2	t_3	t_4	t_5
$\hat{\kappa}^t_E$	[0.5,0.7]	[0.4,0.6]	[0.4,0.6]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]	[0.3,0.4]
$\hat{\kappa}^t_I$	[0.6,0.8]	[0.5,0.7]	[0.5,0.7]	[0.4,0.6]	[0.4,0.6]	[0.4,0.6]
$\hat{\kappa}^t_N$	[0.7,0.9]	[0.6,0.8]	[0.6,0.8]	[0.5,0.4]	[0.5,0.4]	[0.5,0.4]

	0	t_1	t_2	t_3	t_4	t_5
σ^t_E	0.2	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.6
σ^t_I	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.7	0.7	0.7
σ^t_N	0.3	0.5	0.5	0.8	0.8	0.8

By calculations verify that \mathcal{C}^t is a t-NCID of X. But it is not a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of X since $\hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}(0 * t_1) \not\geq \hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}(t_1)$ and $\sigma^t_{\Xi}(0 * t_1) \not\leq \sigma^t_{\Xi}(t_1), \forall t_1 \in X$.

Corollary 5.7 Every t-NCSU which satisfies N4 and N5 becomes a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal.

Theorem 5.8 Every t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of a BF-algebra X is also a t-NCSU of X.

Proof. Suppose $\mathcal{C}^t = \{\hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}, \sigma^t_{\Xi}\}$ be a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of X, then for any $t_1 \in X$ we have $\hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}(0 * t_1) \geq \hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}(t_1)$ and $\sigma^t_{\Xi}(0 * t_1) \leq \sigma^t_{\Xi}(t_1)$. Now by N4, N6, Proposition 3.3, we know that $\hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}((t_1 * t_2) * (0 * t_2)), \hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}(0 * t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}(t_1), \hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}(0 * t_2)\} \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}(t_1), \hat{\kappa}^t_{\Xi}(t_2)\}$ and $\sigma^t_{\Xi}(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma^t_{\Xi}((t_1 * t_2) * (0 * t_2)), \sigma^t_{\Xi}(0 * t_2)\} = \max\{\sigma^t_{\Xi}(t_1), \sigma^t_{\Xi}(0 * t_2)\} \leq \max\{\sigma^t_{\Xi}(t_1), \sigma^t_{\Xi}(t_2)\}$. Hence \mathcal{C}^t is a t-neutrosophic cubic subalgebra of X.

Theorem 5.9 The R-intersection of any set of t-NCIDs of X is a t-NCID of X.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{C}^t_i = \{(\hat{\kappa}^t_i)_{\Xi}, (\sigma^t_i)_{\Xi}\}$ where $i \in k$, be a collection of sets of t-NCID of X and $t_1, t_2 \in X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap (\hat{\kappa}^t_i)_{\Xi})(0) &= \text{rinf}(\hat{\kappa}^t_i)_{\Xi}(0) \\ &\geq \text{rinf}(\hat{\kappa}^t_i)_{\Xi}(t_1) \\ &= (\bigcap (\hat{\kappa}^t_i)_{\Xi})(t_1) \\ &\Rightarrow (\bigcap (\hat{\kappa}^t_i)_{\Xi})(0) \geq (\bigcap (\hat{\kappa}^t_i)_{\Xi})(t_1), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(0) = \sup(\sigma_i^t)_\Xi(0) \\
 & \leq (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi(t_1) \\
 & = (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1) \\
 & \Rightarrow (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(0) \leq (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1), \\
 & (\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1) = \text{rinf}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi(t_1) \\
 & \geq \text{rinf}\{\text{rmin}\{(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi(t_1 * t_2), (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi(t_2)\}\} \\
 & = \text{rmin}\{\text{rinf}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi(t_1 * t_2), \text{rinf}(\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi(t_2)\} \\
 & = \text{rmin}\{(\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1 * t_2), (\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi)(t_2)\} \\
 & \Rightarrow (\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{(\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1 * t_2), (\cap (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_\Xi)(t_2)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1) = \sup(\sigma_i^t)_\Xi(t_1) \\
 & \leq \sup\{\max\{(\sigma_i^t)_\Xi(t_1 * t_2), (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi(t_2)\}\} \\
 & = \max\{\sup(\sigma_i^t)_\Xi(t_1 * t_2), \sup(\sigma_i^t)_\Xi(t_2)\} \\
 & = \max\{(\vee (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1 * t_2), (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_2)\} \\
 & \Rightarrow (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1) \leq \max\{(\vee (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_1 * t_2), (\vee (\sigma_i^t)_\Xi)(t_2)\},
 \end{aligned}$$

which show that R-intersection is a t-NCID of X.

Theorem 5.10 The R-intersection of any set of t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideals of X is also a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of X.

Proof. It is similar to the proof of Theorem 5.9.

Theorem 5.11 For a t-neutrosophic cubic ideal $\mathcal{C}^t = \{\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t, \sigma_\Xi^t\}$ of X, the following assertions are valid:

1. if $t_1 * t_2 \leq z$, then $\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_2), \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_3)\}$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1) \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_2), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_3)\}$,
2. if $t_1 \leq t_2$, then $\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_1) \geq \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_2)$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1) \leq \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)$, $\forall t_1, t_2, t_3 \in X$.

Proof. 1. Assume that $t_1, t_2, t_3 \in X$ such that $t_1 * t_2 \leq t_3$. Then $(t_1 * t_2) * t_3 = 0$ and thus $\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2), \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_2)\} \geq \text{rmin}\{\text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t((t_1 * t_2) * t_3), \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_3)\}, \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{\text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(0), \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_3)\}, \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_2), \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_3)\}$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1) \leq \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\} \leq \max\{\max\{\sigma_\Xi^t((t_1 * t_2) * t_3), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_3)\}, \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\} = \max\{\max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(0), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_3)\}, \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\} = \max\{\sigma_\Xi^t(b), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_3)\}$.

2. Again, take $t_1, t_2 \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq t_2$. Then $t_1 * t_2 = 0$ and thus $\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2), \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(0), \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_2)\} = \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_2)$ and $\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1) \leq \text{rmin}\{\sigma_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{\sigma_\Xi^t(0), \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)\} = \sigma_\Xi^t(t_2)$.

Theorem 5.12 Let $\mathcal{C}^t = \{\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t, \sigma_\Xi^t\}$ is a neutrosophic cubic ideal of X. If $t_1 * t_2 \leq t_1, \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$. Then \mathcal{C}^t is a t-NCSU of X.

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{C}^t = \{\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t, \sigma_\Xi^t\}$ is a t-neutrosophic cubic ideal of X. Suppose that $t_1 * t_2 \leq t_1 \forall t_1, t_2 \in X$. Then

$$\hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \hat{\kappa}_\Xi^t(t_1) \quad (\because \text{By Theorem 5.11})$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} \quad (\because \text{By N4}) \\ &\geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} \quad (\because \text{By Theorem 5.11}) \\ &\Rightarrow \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} &\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \quad (\because \text{By Theorem 5.11}) \\ &\leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} \quad (\because \text{By N5}) \\ &\leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} \quad (\because \text{By Theorem 5.11}) \\ &\Rightarrow \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2) \leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\mathcal{C}^t = \{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t\}$ is a t-NCSU of X.

Theorem 5.13 If $\mathcal{C}^t = \{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t\}$ is a t-neutrosophic cubic ideal of X, then $(\dots((t_1 * x_1) * x_2) * \dots) * x_n = 0$ for any $t_1, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n \in X \Rightarrow \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(x_1), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(x_2), \dots, \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(x_n)\}$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(x_1), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(x_2), \dots, \sigma_{\Xi}^t(x_n)\}$.

Proof. We can prove this theorem by using induction on n and Theorem 5.11.

Theorem 5.14 A t-neutrosophic cubic set $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of X $\Leftrightarrow U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$ and $L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$ are closed ideals of X for every $[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}] \in D[0,1]$ and $t_{\Xi_1} \in [0,1]$.

Proof. Assume that $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of X. For $[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}] \in D[0,1]$, clearly, $0 * t_1 \in U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$, where $t_1 \in X$. Let $t_1, t_2 \in X$ be such that $t_1 * t_2 \in U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$ and $t_2 \in U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$. Then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} \geq [s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}] \Rightarrow t_1 \in U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$. Hence $U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$ is a closed ideal of X.

For $t_{\Xi_1} \in [0,1]$. Clearly, $0 * t_1 \in L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$. Let $t_1, t_2 \in X$ be such that $t_1 * t_2 \in L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$ and $t_2 \in L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$. Then $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1 * t_2), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2)\} \leq t_{\Xi_1} \Rightarrow t_1 \in L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$. Hence $L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$ is a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of X.

Conversely, suppose that each nonempty level subset $U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$ and $L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$ are closed ideals of X. For any $t_1 \in X$, let $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = [s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}]$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) = t_{\Xi_1}$. Then $t_1 \in U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}])$ and $t_1 \in L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$. Since $0 * t_1 \in U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}]) \cap L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t_{\Xi_1})$, it follows that $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0 * t_1) \geq [s_{\Xi_1}, s_{\Xi_2}] = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_1)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(0 * t_1) \leq t_{\Xi_1} = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_1) \quad \forall t_1 \in X$. If there exists $\alpha_{\Xi_1}, \beta_{\Xi_1} \in X$ such that $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\alpha_{\Xi_1}) \leq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\alpha_{\Xi_1} * \beta_{\Xi_1}), \beta_{\Xi_1}\}$, then by taking $[s'_{\Xi_1}, s'_{\Xi_2}] = \frac{1}{2}[\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\alpha_{\Xi_1} * \beta_{\Xi_1}) + \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\alpha_{\Xi_1}), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\beta_{\Xi_1})\}]$.

It follows that $\alpha_{\Xi_1} * \beta_{\Xi_1} \in U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s'_{\Xi_1}, s'_{\Xi_2}])$ and $\beta_{\Xi_1} \in U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s'_{\Xi_1}, s'_{\Xi_2}])$, but $\alpha_{\Xi_1} \notin U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s'_{\Xi_1}, s'_{\Xi_2}])$, which is contradiction. Hence, $U(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t|[s'_{\Xi_1}, s'_{\Xi_2}])$ is not closed ideal of X.

Again, if there exists $\alpha_{\Xi_1}, \beta_{\Xi_1} \in X$ such that $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\alpha_{\Xi_1}) \geq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\alpha_{\Xi_1} * \beta_{\Xi_1}), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\beta_{\Xi_1})\}$, then by taking $t'_{\Xi_1} = \frac{1}{2}[\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\alpha_{\Xi_1} * \beta_{\Xi_1}) + \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\alpha_{\Xi_1}), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\beta_{\Xi_1})\}]$.

It follows that $\alpha_{\Xi_1} * \beta_{\Xi_1} \in L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t'_{\Xi_1})$ and $\beta_{\Xi_1} \in L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t'_{\Xi_1})$, but $\alpha_{\Xi_1} \notin L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t'_{\Xi_1})$, which is contradiction. So $L(\sigma_{\Xi}^t|t'_{\Xi_1})$ is not closed ideal of X. Hence $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is a t-neutrosophic cubic ideal of X because it satisfies N3 and N4.

6 Neutrosophic Cubic Ideals under Homomorphism

In this section, t-neutrosophic cubic ideals are investigated under homomorphism through some results.

Theorem 6.1 Suppose that $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ is a homomorphism of BF-algebra. If $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is a t-NCID of Y . Then pre-image $\Gamma^{-1}(\mathcal{C}^t) = (\Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t), \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t))$ of \mathcal{C}^t under Γ of X is a t-NCID of X .

Proof. For all $t_1 \in X$, $\Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1)) \leq \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(0)) = \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(0)$ and $\Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1)) \geq \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(0)) = \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(0)$. Let $t_1, t_2 \in X, \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1)) \geq \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1) * \Gamma(t_2)), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_2))\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1 * t_2)), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_2))\} = \text{rmin}\{\Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_1 * t_2), \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_2)\}$ and $\Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(a) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1)) \leq \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1) * \Gamma(t_2)), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_2))\} = \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1 * t_2)), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_2))\} = \max\{\Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_1 * t_2), \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_2)\}$. Hence $\Gamma^{-1}(\mathcal{C}^t) = (\Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t), \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t))$ is a t-NCID of X .

Corollary 6.2 A homomorphic pre-image of a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal is a t-NCID.

Proof. Using Proposition 5.5 and Theorem 6.1, we can prove this corollary .

Corollary 6.3 A homomorphic preimage of a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal is also a t-NCID.

Proof. Using Theorem 5.8 and Theorem 6.1, we can prove this corollary.

Corollary 6.4 Let $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism of BF-algebra. If $\mathcal{C}_i^t = ((\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})$ is a t-NCID of Y where $i \in k$ then the pre image $\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in kR} (\mathcal{C}_i^t)_{\Xi}) = (\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in kR} (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}),$

$\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in kR} (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}))$ is a t-NCID of X .

Proof. Using Theorem 5.9 and Theorem 6.1, we can prove this corollary.

Corollary 6.5 Let $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ be a homomorphism of BF-algebra. If $\mathcal{C}_i^t = ((\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}, (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi})$ is a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideals of Y where $i \in k$ then the pre-image $\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in kR} (\mathcal{C}_i^t)_{\Xi}) = (\Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in kR} (\hat{\kappa}_i^t)_{\Xi}), \Gamma^{-1}(\bigcap_{i \in kR} (\sigma_i^t)_{\Xi}))$ is a t-neutrosophic cubic closed ideal of X .

Proof. Straightforward, using Theorem 5.10 and Theorem 6.1.

Theorem 6.6 Suppose that $\Gamma|X \rightarrow Y$ is an epimorphism of BF-algebra. Then $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is a t-NCID of Y , if $\Gamma^{-1}(\mathcal{C}^t) = (\Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t), \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t))$ of \mathcal{C}^t under Γ of X is a t-NCID of X .

Proof. For any $t_2 \in Y, \exists t_1 \in X$ such that $t_2 = \Gamma(t_1)$. Then $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1)) = \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(t_1) \leq \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)(0) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(0)) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(0)$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t(t_2) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(t_1)) = \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(t_1) \geq \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)(0) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma(0)) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(0)$.

Suppose $(t_2)_1, (t_2)_2 \in Y$. Then $\Gamma((t_1)_1) = (t_2)_1$ and $\Gamma((t_1)_2) = (t_2)_2$ for some $(t_1)_1, (t_1)_2 \in X$. Thus $\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t((t_2)_1) = \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma((t_1)_1)) = \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)((t_1)_1) \geq \text{rmin}\{\Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)((t_1)_1 * (t_1)_2), \Gamma^{-1}(\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t)((t_1)_2)\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma((t_1)_1 * (t_1)_2)), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma((t_1)_2))\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma((t_1)_1) * \Gamma((t_1)_2)), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma((t_1)_2))\} = \text{rmin}\{\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t((t_2)_1 * (t_2)_2), \hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t((t_2)_2)\}$ and $\sigma_{\Xi}^t((t_2)_1) = \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma((t_1)_1)) = \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)((t_1)_1) \leq \max\{\Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)((t_1)_1 * (t_1)_2), \Gamma^{-1}(\sigma_{\Xi}^t)((t_1)_2)\} = \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma((t_1)_1) * \Gamma((t_1)_2)), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma((t_1)_2))\} = \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma((t_1)_1) * \Gamma((t_1)_2)), \sigma_{\Xi}^t(\Gamma((t_1)_2))\} = \max\{\sigma_{\Xi}^t((t_2)_1 * (t_2)_2), \sigma_{\Xi}^t((t_2)_2)\}$.

Hence $\mathcal{C}^t = (\hat{\kappa}_{\Xi}^t, \sigma_{\Xi}^t)$ is a t-NCID of Y .

7 Conclusion

In this paper, the concept of t-neutrosophic cubic set was defined and investigated it on BF-algebra through several useful results. For future work this study will provide base for t-neutrosophic soft cubic set, t-neutrosophic soft cubic (M-subalgebra, normal ideals) and different algebras like G-algebra and B-algebra.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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